

LAGOS
STATE
UNIVERSITY

Journal of

MANAGEMENT
AND
SOCIAL SCIENCES

ISSN: 978-33424-4-4

Volume 19 No. 4
November 2025

Published By
Lagos State University
Ojo, Lagos State

eliteworksrp.com.ng/lasu/home.html

Lagos State University
Ojo, Nigeria

LASU JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT AND SOCIAL SCIENCES

ISSN: 978-33424-4-4

LASU Journal of Management and Social Sciences is a multi-disciplinary journal published by the Lagos State University, Nigeria. Its major aim is to serve as rallying-point for intellectual brainstorming and to contribute towards the attainment of sustainable development in Nigeria by providing a forum for ideas initiated and empirically tested by research experts to be published for the benefit of Policy Makers, Administrators and other functionaries in both the private and public sectors of the Nigerian economy.

- MISSION STATEMENT -

LASU Journal of Management and Social Sciences' major aim is to serve as rallying-point for intellectual brainstorming and to contribute towards the attainment of sustainable development in Nigeria by providing a forum for ideas initiated and empirically tested by research experts to be published for the benefit of Policy Makers, Administrators and other functionaries in both the private and public sectors of the Nigerian economy.

The belief is that an information bank such as this would be beneficial for poverty

reduction, technological advancement, good governance and other drivers of sustainable development.

The article must be original and should not be more than 15 pages in length including references. All manuscripts are reviewed by three referees/assessors and at least, one member of the Editorial Board. The writing style should be clear and lucid. Emphasis is placed on readability, high scholarly standards and works that have policy implications on sustainable development in Africa, and by extension, the international community.

- INFORMATION FOR CONTRIBUTORS -

Submissions are published on the understanding that they have not been published elsewhere. More than two papers by the same author(s) may not be accepted for publication in any one edition. While single authorship is accepted, premium is placed on co-authored manuscript(s). Credit is given to local examples and inferences. All works cited in the text should be listed under references in alphabetical order. A pre-publication proof of all manuscripts that passes final editorial screening is prepared for authors' verification (if required). Unaccepted manuscripts are not returned to the author(s).

The Editorial Board reserves the right to modify or condense manuscripts where it is unavoidable to meet its standard/specifications. Such decision is final. The author(s) of manuscript(s) published in the journal are entitled to receive only one (1) copy of the journal. Manuscripts are accepted throughout the year and are placed before the Editorial Board/Reviewer(s) on the basis of first to come, first to be served. The opinions expressed in this Journal are entirely those of the authors. The publisher of this Journal does not guarantee the accuracy of the information therein and cannot not accept any responsibility whatsoever for the consequences of their use.

FOR MORE INFORMATION, CONTACT:

The Editor
LASU Journal of Management and Social Sciences
Lagos State University
Ojo, Nigeria.
E-mail: eliteworksrp@gmail.com

Lagos State University
Ojo, Nigeria

LASU JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT AND SOCIAL SCIENCES

ISSN: 978-33424-4-4

EDITORIAL BOARD

Editor-In-Chief

Ojo A. Kayode

Editorial Committee

Wusu, Onipede

Adeola, G. L.

Ajiboye, O. E.

Odubunmi, A. S.

Adejobi, O. S.

Yusuf, R. O.

Opaleye, Victoria

Advisory Board

Adedokun, Laide - Lagos State University Ojo

Momoh, Abubakar

Omobintan, O. A.

Omotayo Ayo

Onifade, Ademola

Fapounda. A.

Oyekanmi. F.A. D. - University of Lagos, Akoka

Gbadegesin, A. S. - University of Ibadan, Nigeria

Aluko, M.A O. - Obafemi Awolowo University

Lagos State University
Ojo, Nigeria

LASU JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT AND SOCIAL SCIENCES

ISSN: 978-33424-4-4

Volume 19 Issue 4, November 2025

CONTENTS

THEORETICAL MODELS FOR ENHANCING OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY THROUGH TECHNOLOGY IN NIGERIAN BUSINESSES Anwuli Nkemchor Obiki-Osafiele, Olajide Soji Osundare, Edith Ebele Agu & Ibrahim Adedeji Adeniran	1
EFFECT OF TALENT RETENTION ON PERFORMANCE OF NNPC DOWNSTREAM OIL SECTOR IN SOUTH EAST, NIGERIA Onyekuru Akudo, Nnadi-Nicholas Eucharua Obiageri & Prof. G. A. Emerole	20
PUSH AND PULL MOTIVATION FACTORS: A PANACEA FOR TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CHALLENGES IN OLUMINRIN WATERFALLS, NIGERIA Folusade Arowosafe & Oyebola Akinwotu	30
TALENT MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND SALES PERFORMANCE OF DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN UMUAHIA, ABIA STATE, NIGERIA Chinaza Olive Jacob, Victor Monday Dibie (PhD.) & Chinwe Obiora Onuba (PhD.)	41
MAKING USE OF OPERATIONS RESEARCH TECHNIQUES IN NIGERIAN BUSINESS ORGANIZATIONS Ighomereho, O. Salome	58
EFFECT OF SUCCESSION PLANNING ON ORGANIZATIONAL PRODUCTIVITY OF TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN SOUTH-SOUTH Okon, Nse Bassey, J. C. Ihemeje (PhD.) & S. M. Okebaram (PhD.)	76
ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND SALES PERFORMANCE Victor Rupert Otu, Victor Monday Dibie (PhD.) & Emmanuel Linus Unanam	89

ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND SALES PERFORMANCE

* Victor Rupert Otu

** Victor Monday Dibie (PhD.)

*** Emmanuel Linus Unanam

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17863503>

ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of organizational culture on sales performance in Brewery in Nigeria. The study examined the effect of market culture, adhocracy culture, and hierarchy culture on sales performance in Nigeria Brewery. To achieve these objectives, the study adopted descriptive survey research design and collected primary data through the use of questionnaire. The study population is made up of 350 staff of Nigeria Brewery Aba, Abia State, Nigeria, while the sample size is 187 after adopting Taro Yamane formula. Multiple regression analysis was used to analyze the data, and the findings reveal that market culture, adhocracy culture, and hierarchy culture have a significant effect on sales performance in Nigeria Breweries Plc. Based on the findings, the study recommends that firms should focus on developing a culture that prioritizes product/service availability, durability, and customer satisfaction. Business managers should assess the effectiveness of their organizational culture by implementing business strategies such as well-defined mission and vision, core corporate values, employee-focused leadership, and consistency. If these strategies are not currently in place, business managers should develop an effective organizational culture for their company using these strategies. By paying attention to these factors, firms can improve their sales performances.

Keywords: Organizational Culture, Sales Performance

INTRODUCTION

Organizational culture, as an idea, has been explored in various disciplines including social human studies and modern administrative intellectual research (Schein, 2010) stated in Alshamari (2017). The word culture has been gotten from thought of human development which implies the examples of unique thinking and behavior of certain group of people in an organization or within a geographical area. The unvarying behavior of people in an organization is known as "corporate culture" (Childress, 2013). Culture is a general concept that since time immemorial has been an integral part of society. It is traditionally described as a people's way of life or worldview. This assumes that a certain group of people have

*** Corresponding Author:**

VICTOR RUPERT OTU

GZ Industries Ltd Aba, Abia State, Nigeria.

**** Co-Author:**

VICTOR MONDAY DIBIE (PhD.)

Department of Marketing,
College of Management Science,
Michael Okpara University of Agriculture,
Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria.

***** Co-Author:**

EMMANUEL LINUS UNANAM

Department of Marketing,
Faculty of Management Sciences,
Akwa Ibom State University,
Ikot Akpaden, Nigeria.

common values that all of their members hold. According to Alshamari (2017), there are misunderstandings about the notion that culture cannot be reduced to the idea of uniformity alone. Each individual within a social group has personal values that may occasionally clash with the group's overall values. Because it incorporates a variety of individual, plural, and collective viewpoints, culture is complicated. According to Schneider *et al.*, (2013), "organizational culture refers to the beliefs and values that have existed in an organization for a long time, as well as to the beliefs of the staff and the foreseen value of their work that will influence their attitudes and behavior." This is just one of the many definitions of the term as defined by numerous authors. In a similar vein, organizational culture is a collection of guidelines and indicators that organizations can use to indicate how they may vary from one another (Childress, 2013).

However, Kotter (2012) asserts that there are two main components to organizational culture: material and non-material cultures. The material aspects of culture include products of industry, technology, and art, and are directly observable. The non-material aspects of culture consist of the knowledge, philosophy, morals, languages, motivation, attitudes, values, and norms shared and transmitted in society. They are not visible or tangible but they are manifested through the psychological states and behaviour of a people. The corporate culture is utilized to make sense of the more popularized significance of hierarchical culture. An association's way of life over the course of the ten years has progressively significant for ordinary authoritative working since it is accept to influence execution. The presentation the board challenge has similarly stood out of specialists in administration. An investigation of culture inside the association shows that laborers think the same way and are directed by similar thoughts regarding the business (Racelis, 2010). There has been huge examination in the writing to investigate the effect of authoritative culture on representative execution and efficiency. For example, researchers (Hofstede, 2010; Kotter, 2012) guarantee that authoritative culture could be utilized for estimating financial execution of an association.

Numerous business directors battle to get by in a cutthroat worldwide market as a result of testing qualities in business (Bolboli & Reiche, 2014). The difficulties incorporate expanding worldwide cost contest and fulfilling requests of various partners. Throughout recent many years, there have been exceptional changes in authoritative administration on the planet (Schein, 2010). This has been credited to new forceful rivalry in the commercial center close by the developing different workers in numerous associations (Rehman, 2012). The intricacy of business climate has likewise constrained associations to look for more proficient administration methodologies. Thus, an emphasis on hierarchical culture is getting extraordinary unmistakable quality in the business area. As indicated by Kotter (2012) hierarchical culture straightforwardly affects various authoritative factors. Research additionally shows that assuming representatives are directed by similar standards and values in their association, their presentation would improve (Hofstede, 2017). The examples of overcoming adversity of presumed associations uncover that supported upper hand could be credited to proceeded with inside development through a bunch of convictions, esteems and shared standards in the association. These convictions, values and standards represent the way of life of an association and capability as a wellspring of the executives rehearses for the association. It vigorously impacts direction, strategy plan, administration style and in general work space inside an association (Morcos, 2018).

Statement of the Problem

Many business managers struggle to survive in a competitive global market because of challenging characteristics in business activities. Increasing global price competition and meeting the demands of various stakeholders are among the difficulties (Bolboli & Reiche, 2014). Establishing an effective organizational culture, which is crucial to raising performance and productivity, is more difficult for managers in corporate groups (Kenny,

2021). Profitability is a critical factor for the existence of any business, and expanding the business scope is also essential for business growth. Business managers in a corporate group face more difficulties than managers in a single company when it comes to creating an effective culture in diverse organizations (Lee & Gaur, 2013). Poor cultural integration in diversified businesses has an impact on the corporate group's financial performance and the value of its shareholders, according to Idris *et al.*, (2015). According to Bolboli and Reiche (2014), a lack of cultural integration among company managers within the corporate group is the reason why over 90% of business excellence initiatives fail. Inconsistent culture or guideline that exists within the group is a major barrier to corporate performance (Weber & Tarba, 2020). One of the main reasons for the corporate group's low performance and productivity is the absence of an effective organizational culture (Eaton & Kilby, 2015). As a result, in a corporate group, poor cultural integration and an ineffective organizational culture have an impact on sales performance and lower shareholder return (Idris *et al.*, 2015). According to Eaton and Kilby (2015), only 25% of corporate leaders identified an effective organizational culture for their company, despite 72% of them acknowledging the significance of organizational culture to organizational performance (Dibie, Nto, Unanam & Bassey, 2019). The general business issue is that some managers of corporate firms do not have an effective organizational culture, which frequently leads to diminished productivity and poor performance within the corporate group. The specific business problem is that some senior company managers lack strategies to establish an effective organizational culture to improve performance. Thus, this study sought to find out the effect of organizational culture on sales performance.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to assess the organizational culture and sales performance in Nigeria Brewery Plc, Aba, Abia State Nigeria. The specific objectives include to:

- a) examine the effect of market culture on sales performance in Nigeria Brewery Plc
- b) examine the effect of adhocracy culture on sales performance in Nigeria Brewery Plc
- c) examine the effect of hierarchy culture on sales performance in Nigeria Brewery Plc

Scope and Significance of the Study

The study centered on organizational culture and sales performance. The study focused on the role of market culture, adhocracy culture and hierarchy culture on sales performance. Geographically, the study was carried out in Nigeria breweries Plc, Aba, Abia State, Nigeria. Also, employees of Nigeria breweries Plc, Aba were used as unit of analysis. However, the results will be useful to business managers in the public and private sector who face the challenges of improving performance and productivity for their organization. The study findings will assist business managers in the corporate group by contributing knowledge and experiences regarding the role of organizational culture in improving performance and productivity in the organization. The study results included valuable information for business managers about how to establish an organizational culture to enhance performance and productivity in the corporate group. Finally, the study will serve as a reference material to future researchers who would want to conduct similar research in future.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Organizational Culture

One definition of culture is "the way of life for an entire society." According to Schein (2010), a group's culture is "a pattern of shared basic assumptions that the group learned as it solved its problems of external adaptation and internal integration that has

worked well enough to be considered valid and, therefore, to be taught to new members as the correct way to perceive, think, and feel in relation to those problems." Through informal, non-structural means—shared values, beliefs, understandings, and norms—culture serves as the social glue that maintains an organization's integration and control. In this way, culture helps to prevent tension, conflict, and fragmentation. Culture can direct and mold attitudes and behaviors by acting as a sense-making and control-gaining mechanism. Organizational cultures, according to King (2012), are a set of values that subtly and silently influence every decision and choice made within the company. The norms that members of an organization experience and characterize as their work environments are part of the organization's culture. According to Schneider et al. (2013), organizational culture is a collection of shared values, symbols, and customs among the members of a particular company that characterizes how things are carried out in an organization to address issues with internal management as well as those pertaining to suppliers and customers and environment. Despite the fact that there is no universally accepted definition of organizational culture, a quick glance at the majority of definitions revealed that they all share a number of distinct traits. First of all, they all incorporate the idea of sharing, suggesting that group dynamics are the only way that organizational culture is formed. Second, it is believed that organizational culture is a social construct that is influenced by the location, history, working conditions, and particular events of each organization and its employees.

Types of Organizational Culture

The four types of organizational culture include (a) clan culture, (b) adhocracy culture, (c) hierarchy culture, and (d) market culture (Sok *et al.*, 2014; Wiewiora *et al.*, 2014). Clan or supportive culture contains an employee-oriented leadership, cohesiveness, participation, and teamwork (Han, 2012). Adhocracy or an entrepreneurial culture includes innovative, creative, and adaptable characteristics. Hierarchy culture, according to Sok et al. (2014), is a set of rules and guidelines used to manage organizational activities. According to Pinho et al. (2014), market culture encompasses both competition and the accomplishment of organizational objectives. Human affiliation, teamwork, attachment, trust, loyalty, and support are among the presumptions and values of clan culture (Fiordelisi, 2014). In a clan culture, managers must act democratically to encourage and inspire staff to create an excellence culture within the company (Miguel, 2015). In an effective organizational culture, interpersonal relationships are active. When people believe in, are loyal to, and own the organization, they behave well and grow to feel a sense of ownership (Nongo & Ikyanyon, 2012). Clan culture encompasses open communication, teamwork, participation, and employee involvement. In a clan culture, business managers encourage teamwork and employee empowerment (Yirdaw, 2014). The ultimate goal of clan culture is improving employee performance through commitment, sense of ownership, and responsibility (Han, 2012).

In adhocracy or an entrepreneurial culture, organization members may require clarification for their job assignments including the importance and impact of the assignment to achieve organizational goals. The values and assumptions of adhocracy culture include (a) growth, (b) risk taking, (c) creativity, (d) diversity, (e) independence, and (f) adaptability (Hartnell *et al.*, 2011). Business managers who operate in an adhocracy culture devote more funds to research and development and support staff members' participation in original and creative research projects (Sok et al., 2014). Innovation and creativity are crucial in an adhocracy culture to boost output and improve services provided by the company. Innovation and change are the ultimate outcomes of an adhocracy culture (Fiordelisi, 2014). Adhocracy culture and innovative entrepreneurial orientation are positively correlated, according to research findings in the field of organizational culture (Engelen et al., 2014). In a competition culture, organizational members have clear objectives to increase their reward through market

achievement (Han, 2012). Competition culture includes (a) gathering customer and competitor information, (b) appropriate goal setting, planning and decision-making, and (c) task focus leadership. Competition culture also contains market aggressiveness and achievement. The competition culture includes open communication, competition, competence, and achievement (Miguel, 2015).

1. Market Culture and Performance

A market culture is regarded as a results-oriented workplace with emphasis on winning, outpacing the competition, escalating share price, and market leadership (Cameron, 2018). Maintaining a close relationship with customers can lead to intense brand loyalty, collaborative product development efforts, and timely market information, all of which improve financial performance (Peters & Waterman, 2019). As long as they can adjust to their surroundings (pertaining to their industry and business conditions), organizational culture can also have an impact on performance (Kim et al., 2020). An increasingly important component of superior corporate performance is a market-oriented corporate culture. According to their research, a corporate culture that is focused on the market encourages organizational innovation, which in turn influences the performance of the company. Fekete and financial performance in an empirical investigation. According to these researchers, market culture prioritizes external factors and emphasizes efficacy, efficiency, and competitiveness, all of which enhance performance outcomes. Characteristic specific to market culture seem to be external oriented and play an important role in adapting companies to their external environment.

2. Adhocracy Culture and Performance

Adhocracy culture is characterized as a dynamic, entrepreneurial, innovative and creative workplace (Cameron, 2020; Tseng, 2010). It emphasizes new product and service development, adaptability, growth, change, productivity, efficiency and experimentation. These traits have improved corporate performance and knowledge conversion, and they reflect an external orientation (Tseng, 2010). Performance outcomes may be positively impacted by an organizational culture that is characterized by flexibility in response to its external environment (Kim et al., 2020). According to Ogbonna & Harris (2010), innovative and competitive cultures have a positive correlation with organizational performance. Fekete and impact the companies' financial performance. Adhocracy culture-related traits appear to have a significant impact on performance results.

3. Hierarchy Culture and Performance

Hierarchy culture is commonly thought to be characterized by formalized, structured environments, procedures, well-defined processes, and an efficient organization (Cameron, 2004). Stability, predictability, and efficiency are the long-term concerns of this kind of culture (Cameron, 2020; Tseng, 2010). Tseng (2010) argued that more formalized companies typically have formalized controls and processes, so their corporate performance is better due to their effective management, even though studies show hierarchy culture is not the best performer when compared to other cultural dimensions. According to Ogbonna and Haris (2010), bureaucratic cultures and organizational performance are unrelated. Financial performance is negatively impacted by hierarchy culture, according to empirical results from the Fekete study.

Sales Performance

The foundation of business is sales, which is the meeting of buyers and sellers in various locations that, if successful in negotiating the exchange of products, help the business achieve its objectives. Contacting potential clients to learn about their needs, showcasing and demonstrating products, negotiating prices, and handling delivery and payment are all parts of the sales process. The quantity of goods sold over a specific time period is known as sales

performance. Behrman and Perreault (1982) defined sales performance as having a high degree of abstraction and a wide scope. The broad and long-term goals that comprise the concept of sales include finding and cultivating key accounts in one's territory, surpassing sales quotas and objectives, and gaining a significant market share performance. Sales performance is crucial to every company's success, especially in competitive markets. Understanding and quantifying sales performance is crucial for assessing salespeople and identifying areas for development. Organizations frequently use a variety of key performance indicators (KPIs) and metrics to measure sales performance accurately. Sales revenue, units sold, average transaction value, conversion rates, sales cycle length, customer satisfaction ratings, and customer acquisition and retention rates are a few examples. Businesses can learn more about the success of their sales tactics and pinpoint areas for development by examining these metrics (Behrman & Perreault, 2019).

Theoretical Review

Several theories have been formulated to show the inherent connection between organizational practices and performance. For the purpose of this article, Schein's theory of organizational culture was used.

Schein's Theory of Organizational Culture

The three domains of the theory are artifacts, espoused values, and fundamental underlying assumptions. Artifacts are the visible, palpable, and surface-level manifestations of an organization's culture that can be found in its products, physical surroundings, language, technology, apparel, published values, myths and stories, rituals, and ceremonies. Strategies, objectives, common perceptions, common presumptions, norms, and beliefs and values instilled by founders and leaders are examples of espoused beliefs and values. The fundamental underlying assumptions of an organization are the deeply ingrained, unconscious, and taken-for-granted presumptions that are shared with others, according to Hoque et al. (2013). Any challenge to these presumptions will cause defensiveness and anxiety, which will impair the stability required for effective performance. Unquestionably, strong values in the form of well-defined objectives and strategies are necessary for good performance, and an organization that lacks these qualities will exhibit poor performance attributes. According to this theory, in order to improve organizational performance, an organization's culture should reflect its fundamental artifacts, proclaimed values, and underlying presumptions.

Empirical Review

Etalong and Chikeleze (2023) investigated the connection between organizational culture and employee performance. This study utilized both descriptive and exploratory research methodologies, incorporating primary and secondary data collection instruments. A total of 100 employees from the Enugu State Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning, the Enugu State Civil Service Commission, the Enugu State Economic Planning Commission, and the Office of the Head of Service participated by completing a structured questionnaire, which served as the primary source of data. The analysis of the collected data was conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (IBM SPSS) to test the proposed hypotheses. The results revealed that organizational norms significantly influence employee commitment, particularly regarding professional growth and development, recognition and rewards for exemplary performance, effective communication of the organization's goals and values, and the establishment of a positive work environment. Furthermore, a well-organized work routine notably enhances employee productivity, time management, and the quality of work completed. The study strongly recommends that the Ministries, Departments, and Agencies (MDAs) involved implement and maintain robust organizational norms that promote employee commitment, with a specific emphasis on professional development, recognition and rewards for outstanding performance, clear

communication of organizational objectives and values, and a supportive work environment conducive to high performance.

In order to better understand and test the relationship between organizational culture components and performance, Han (2012) investigated how management practices in Pakistan were affected by organizational culture. Through the use of regression and correlation analysis, the study discovered that among the cultural characteristics that had a significant impact on management practices were consistency and adaptability. The impact of organizational culture on performance management in the insurance sector was examined by Murphy et al. (2013). Five variables—adaptive perspective, communal, network, mercenary, and fragmented culture—were the focus of the study. The study found a connection between management practices and organizational cultures. Nonetheless, the study found that the degree of acceptance of performance management varied among organizational culture types. Akinyomi (2012) investigated the impact of culture on organizational performance in textile companies in Nigeria. Additionally, the study sought to identify the nature of the relationship, performance determinants, and the ways in which culture interacted with other elements within the organizations. The study, which combined qualitative and quantitative methods, discovered that workers seemed to have adopted the industrial way of life regardless of their cultural backgrounds. The study also found a strong correlation between the cultural factors and employee attrition, positive work attitude, and level of commitment. However, there was no direct correlation between these cultural factors and better organizational performance.

At the National Agency for Food and Drugs Administration and Control in Nigeria, Asif and Sajjid (2010) examined the impact of organizational culture on workers' performance. They found a strong correlation between organizational culture and higher levels of employee commitment and productivity. Alshamari (2017) investigated how organizational culture affected the performance of telecom companies in Mogadishu, Somalia. According to the study's correlation coefficient, academic success significantly improved the cultures of competition, entrepreneurship, and consensus. In another study by Nongo and Ikyanyon (2012) on the impact of organizational culture on employees' job performance in Software Houses in Pakistan, customer service, risk-taking and communication system, participation, reward system and innovation were found to have a positively significant impact on organizational job performance.

METHODOLOGY

This study is basically a descriptive survey research and therefore required the use of survey method of investigation. This study was conducted in Abia State, Nigeria. The population of the study consists of the management and staff of Nigeria Breweries Plc, Aba, Abia State. The total population of management and staff of Nigeria breweries Plc is 350 (Field Survey, 2024) which represent the population size of the study. To ensure the determination of accurate sample size, the statistical formula derived by Taro Yamane formula was employed to determine 187 sample size. The main instrument for data collection is a well-structured questionnaire. The statistics table format was used for testing the research question while the multiple regression method was used for testing the hypotheses. The variables that were used were classified in two dependent and independent variables. In the data regressed and collected, the dependent is Y (response variable) while the independent is X (explanatory variable), the specification of the variable is given by: $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \mu_t$

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS**Data Presentation****Table 1: Distribution of Questionnaire and Response Rate**

Total copies of questionnaire	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Number returned	160	85
Number not returned	27	15
Total	187	100

Source: Field survey, 2024

From table 1, 85% of the respondents responded and return their questionnaire while 15% of the questionnaire was null and void.

Table 2: Question one: Market culture affect sales performance of Nigeria breweries Plc.

Option	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	80	50
Agree	60	37.5
Undecided	4	2.5
Disagree	8	5
Strongly disagree	8	5
Total	160	100

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 2 shows that 50 percent of the total respondent strongly agree and 37.5 percent agree that market culture affect sales performance of Nigeria breweries Plc, 5 percent disagree, 5 percent strongly disagree while 2.5 percent undecided.

Table 3: Question Two: Adhocracy Culture Affect Sales Performance of Nigeria Breweries Plc.

Option	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	60	37.5
Agree	60	37.5
Undecided	24	15
Disagree	8	12.5
Strongly disagree	8	12.5
Total	160	100

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 3 shows that 37.5 percent of the respondent strongly agree and 37.5 percent agree that adhocracy culture affect sales performance of Nigeria breweries Plc., 12.5 percent disagree, 12.5 percent strongly disagree, while 15 percent undecided.

Table 4: Question three: Hierarchy culture affects sales performance of Nigeria breweries Plc.

Option	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	68	42.5
Agree	60	37.5
Undecided	8	5
Disagree	16	10
Strongly disagree	8	5
Total	160	100

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 4 shows that 42.5 percent of the total respondents strongly agree that hierarchy culture affect sales performance of Nigeria breweries Plc., 37.5 percent agree, 10 percent disagree 5 percent strongly disagree and 5 percent undecided.

Table 5: Sales performance of Nigeria breweries Plc.

Option	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	52	32.5
Agree	60	37.5
Undecided	-	-
Disagree	28	17.5
Strongly disagree	20	12.5
Total	160	100

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 4 revealed that 32.5 percent of the respondents strongly agree and 37.5 percent agree that there is high level of sales performance in Nigeria breweries Plc due to organizational culture. This was followed by 17.5 percent who disagree, while 12.5 percent strongly disagree.

Data Analysis

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.940 ^a	.856	.812	.45444	.735

a. Predictors: (Constant), MARKET CULTURE, ADHOCRACY CULTURE, HIERARCHY CULTURE,

b. Dependent Variable: SALES PERFORMANCE

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	87.369	3	29.123	267.183	.000 ^b
	Residual	110.565	156	.709		
	Total	197.934	159			

a. Dependent Variable: SALES PERFORMANCE

b. Predictors: (Constant), MARKET CULTURE, ADHOCRACY, HIERARCHY CULTURE,

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	-.103	.193		-.534	.596
	MARKET CULTURE	.746	.150	.716	4.975	.001
	ADHOCRACY CULTURE	.120	.127	.128	.946	.003
	HIERARCHY CULTURE	.345	.121	.112	.895	.002

a. Dependent Variable: SALES PERFORMANCE

The coefficient of determination R-square of 0.856 implied that 85.6% of the sample variation in the dependent variable (sales performance) is explained or caused by the explanatory variables (market culture, clan culture, adhocracy culture and hierarchy culture) while 14.4% is unexplained. This remaining 14.4% could be caused by other factors or variables not built into the model. The value of R-square is an indication of a relationship between the dependent variable (sales performance) and independent variable (market culture, adhocracy culture and hierarchy culture). The value of the adjusted R² is 0.812. This shows that the regression line which captures 81.2 per cent of the total variation in (sales performance) is caused by variation in the explanatory variable specified in the model with less than 18.8 per cent accounted for the stochastic error term. The F-statistic was also used to test the overall significant of the model. The F-value of 267.183 is an indication that the model is statistically significant at 5 percent level of significant at degree of freedom df1= 1 and df2= 3. Finally, the test of autocorrelation using Durbin-Watson shows that the Durbin-Watson value of 0.735 falls outside the conclusive region of Durbin-Watson partition curve. Hence, we can clearly say that there exists some degree of autocorrelation.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis one: H_{0i} : Market culture does not significantly affect the sales performance in Nigeria Breweries Plc. The probability value of 0.001 is less than 0.05 the null hypotheses is rejected and we therefore conclude that market culture significantly affects the sales performance in Nigeria Breweries Plc.

Hypothesis two: H_{0iii} : Adhocracy culture does not significantly affect the sales performance in Nigeria Breweries Plc. The probability value of 0.003 is less than 0.05 the null hypotheses is rejected and we therefore conclude that adhocracy culture significantly affects the sales performance in Nigeria Breweries Plc.

Hypothesis three: H_{0iv} : Hierarchy culture does not significantly affect the sales performance in Nigeria Breweries Plc. The probability value of 0.002 is less than 0.05 the null hypotheses is rejected and we therefore conclude that hierarchy culture significantly affect the sales performance in Nigeria Breweries Plc.

Discussion on Findings

Based on the results, the following findings were summarized thus:

- (i) Market culture significantly affects the sales performance in Nigeria Breweries Plc. The results are in line with those of Mba, Okechukwu, and Agwu (2013), who examined how organizational culture affected workers' performance at Nigeria's National Agency for Food and Drugs Administration and Control and found a strong correlation between organizational culture and higher worker commitment and productivity.
- (ii) Adhocracy culture significantly affects the sales performance in Nigeria Breweries Plc. The results corroborate the findings of Shakil (2012), who investigated how organizational culture affected management practices in Pakistan in order to test and broaden knowledge of the relationship between organizational culture components and performance. The study discovered through regression and correlation analysis that some of the cultural traits that had a major impact on management practices were consistency and adaptability.
- (iii) Hierarchy culture significantly affects the sales performance in Nigeria Breweries Plc. The results validate Lorraine, Dorai, and Zubair's (2011) investigation into how organizational culture affects performance management in the insurance sector. The study found a connection between management practices and organizational cultures. Nonetheless, the study found that the degree of acceptance of performance management varied among organizational cultures.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Organizational culture and sales performance at Nigeria Breweries Plc in Aba, Abia State, Nigeria, were the main subjects of the study. Because it has been believed that an organization's culture affects performance, a focus on organizational culture has grown over the past ten years to become a significant part of daily organizational functioning. The problem of performance management has also caught the interest of management researchers. According to an analysis of organizational culture, employees share similar viewpoints and are motivated by similar business concepts. Research on the relationship between organizational culture and sales performance has shown that businesses that successfully cultivate their cultures are likely to see improvements in employee satisfaction and productivity. Since cultural values are observable and quantifiable, it is beneficial to study organizational culture and performance. Therefore, in order to obtain more thorough results when researching how culture affects performance, it is essential to use both financial and non-financial (cultural values, norms) measures. Employees must, in fact, fully assimilate the

organizational culture, and upper management should give clear instructions and guidance to encourage staff to use the culture to further the goals of the business. The study was conducted using Nigeria breweries plc., data collected from the respondents were analyzed using multiple regression analysis. The result of the analysis revealed that market culture, adhocracy culture and hierarchy culture significantly affect the sales performance in Nigeria Breweries Plc.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the findings so far, the recommendations are that:

1. Since the findings revealed that market culture, adhocracy culture and hierarchy culture significantly affect sales performance, it is therefore recommended that firms should pay adequate attention to their culture and ensure that their culture is challenged towards product/service availability and durability as well as customer satisfaction. These will help in improving sales performance.
2. Firms should assess their organizational culture effectiveness by adopting business strategies such as well-defined mission and vision, core corporate values, employee-focused leadership, and consistency. If these strategies do not exist within the company, business managers should develop an effective organizational culture for their company using these strategies.
3. Firms should focus more on the core corporate values such as (a) customer satisfaction, (b) engaged employees and empowerment, (c) balanced life and performance, (d) respect and trust, and (e) quality and excellence. These values are essential to establishing an effective organizational culture in the corporate group and are necessary to change the society.

References

- Akinyomi, O. J. (2012). Organizational culture and performance of faith-based Universities, Ogun State Nigeria. *JORIND* 10 (3), 15-26.
- Alshamari, S., (2017). Organizational culture and organizational performance in the primary health care sector in Qatar: a proposed theoretical framework. *Cross- Cultural Management Journal* 19, (2), 2.
- Asif, M. & Sajjid, W., (2010). Organizational culture and performance: An empirical study of SMEs in Pakistan. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 1, (3) 26-46.
- Behrman, D. N.; Perreault JR, W. D. A (2019). Role stress model of the performance and satisfaction of industrial salespersons. *Journal of Marketing, Chicago*, 48, (4), 9-21.
- Bolboli, S., &Reiche, M. (2014). Culture-based design and implementation of business excellence. *The TQM Journal*, 26, 329-347. doi:10.1108/TQM-01-2014-0015
- Cameron, K. S. (2020). *A process for changing organizational culture*, Retrieved from <http://competingvalues.com/competingvalues.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/A-Process-for-Changing-Organizational-Culture.pdf>
- Cameron, K. S., & Quinn, R. E. (2018). *Diagnosing and changing organizational culture based on the competing values framework*. JosseyBass, San Fransisco. Retrieved from <https://gothamculture.com>
- Childress, J. R. (2013). *Leverage: The CEO's guide to corporate culture* [Kindle Edition version]. Retrieved from <http://www.amazon.com>

- Dibie, V. M., Nto, C. P. O., Unanam, E. L. & Bassey, I. E. (2019). Effect of product innovation on customer acquisition and retention. *International Journal of Marketing and Communication Studies (IJMCS)*, 4 (1), 50 – 62.
- Eaton, D., & Kilby, G. (2015). Does your organizational culture support your business strategy? *Journal for Quality and Participation*, 37(4), 4-7.
- Engelen, A., Flatten, T., Thalmann, J., & Brettel, M. (2014). The effect of organizational culture on entrepreneurial orientation: A comparison between Germany and Thailand. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 52, 732-752. doi:10.1111/jsbm.12052
- Etalong, T. A & Chikeleze, F. O (2023). The effect of organizational culture on employee performance: A survey of selected public sector organizations in Enugu. *Global Journal of Human Resource Management*, 10(3), 51-58.
- Fiordelisi, F., & Ricci, O. (2014). Corporate culture and CEO turnover. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 28, 66-82.
- Han, H. (2012). The relationship among corporate culture, strategic orientation, and financial performance. *Cornell Hospitality Quarterly*, 53, 207-219. doi:10.1177/19389655124435
- Hartnell, C., Ou, A., & Kinicki, A. (2011). Organizational culture and organizational effectiveness: A meta-analytic investigation of the competing values framework's theoretical suppositions. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 96, 677-694. doi:10.1037/a0021987
- Hofstede, G. (2010). *Culture's consequences: Comparing values, behaviors, institutions and organizations across Nations*, Thousand Oaks CA: Sage.
- Idris, S., Wahab, R., & Jaapar, A. (2015). Corporate cultures integration and organizational performance: A conceptual model on the performance of acquiring companies. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 172, 591-595. doi:10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.407
- Kenny, G. (2012). Diversification: Best practices of the leading companies. *Journal of Business Strategy*, 33(1), 12-20. doi:10.1108/02756661211193776
- Kim, S., Lee J., & Yu K. (2004). Corporate culture and organizational performance. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 19 (4).340 359.
- King, M. (2012). Deep culture. *Journal of Popular Culture*, 45, 687-694. doi:10.1111/j.1540 5931.2012.00952.x
- Kotter, J. P., (2012). *Corporate culture and performance*. New York, NY: Free Press.
- Lee, J., & Gaur, A. (2013). Managing multi-business firms: A comparison between Korean Chaebols and diversified U.S. firms. *Journal of World Business*, 48, 443- 454.
- Miguel, P. C. (2015). Receiving a national quality award three times: Recognition of excellence in quality and performance. *The TQM Journal*, 27, 63-78. doi:10.1108/TQM-10-2010-0027
- Morcos, M. (2018). *Organisational Culture: Definition and Trends*. Reseachgate
- Nongo, E. & Ikyanyon, D. (2012). The influence of corporate culture on employee commitment to the organization. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 7(22), 21-28. doi:10.5539/ijbm.v7n22p21

- Ogbonna, E. and Harris, L.C., (2010). Leadership style, organizational culture and performance: Empirical evidence from UK companies. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 1 (4), 766–788
- Peters, T.J. & Waterman, R.H.(1982) . *In Search of Excellence Rrun Companies*. Harper Collins Publishers, London.
- Pinho, J., Rodrigues, A. & Dibb, S. (2014). The role of corporate culture, market orientation, and organizational commitment in organizational performance. *Journal of Management Development*, 33, 374-398. doi:10.1108/JMD-03-2013- 0036
- Racelis, A. D (2010). The influence of organizational culture on performance of Philippine Banks. *Social Science Dilman*, 6(2) 29-49.
- Rehman, H. U., (2012). *Effects of organizational culture on organisation performance*. Researchgate [https:// www. researchgate.net/publication/224008707](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/224008707)
- Schein, E. H., (2010). *Organizational culture and leadership* (4th ed.). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Sok, J., Blomme, R., & Tromp, D. (2014). Positive and negative spillover from work to home: The role of organizational culture and supportive arrangements. *British Journal of Management*, 25, 456-472. doi:10.1111/1467-8551.12058
- Tseng, Shu-Mei. (2010). The correlation between organizational culture and knowledge conversion on corporate performance. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 14 (2), 269-284.
- Weber, Y., & Tarba, S. (2020). Mergers and acquisitions process: The use of corporate culture analysis. *Cross Cultural Management*, 19, 288-303. doi:10.1108/13527601211247053
- Yirdaw, A. (2014). *The role of governance in quality of education in private higher education institutions: Ethiopia as a case study* (Doctoral dissertation). Available from ProQuest Dissertations and Theses database. (UMI No. 3646173)